

THE STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS FOR EDGE CRACK IN ORTHOTROPIC PLATE SUBJECTED TO PIN LOADS

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ABSTRACT

Description is given of a complex variable – variational method to investigate the stress intensity factors(S.I.F.) in orthotropic plate with edge crack subjected to pin loads. Numerical studies reveal that the convergent results are given by a quite simple program which reduces data manipulation and computer time.

KEYWORDS: Orthotropy; Plates; Crack Propagation; Pin Loads; Variational Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

A number of theoretical approaches have been developed to investigate the stress intensity factors(S.I.F.) on crack tip in anisotropic plates. In order to improve the accuracy and efficiency of computation and eliminate the undeterminacy of modelling, a complex-variable variational method is presented. According to the theory of anisotropic elasticity, the stress and displacement series which satisfy all basic equations are established. For the cracked plate subjected to pin loads, the condition of given resultant forces and single valued condition of displacements around the pin holes are satisfied exactly. The stress field and S.I.F. are determined by variational method.

2. ANALYSIS FOR STRESS AND DISPLACEMENT FIELDS

According to two-dimensional theory of anisotropic elasticity, the stress and dis-

placement fields can be expressed[1,2]

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= 2\operatorname{Re}[\mu_1^2 \varphi'(z_1) + \mu_2^2 \psi'(z_2)] \\ \sigma_{yy} &= 2\operatorname{Re}[\varphi'(z_1) + \psi'(z_2)] \\ \sigma_{xy} &= -2\operatorname{Re}[\mu_1 \varphi'(z_1) + \mu_2 \psi'(z_2)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_x &= 2\operatorname{Re}[p_1 \varphi(z_1) + p_2 \psi(z_2)] \\ u_y &= 2\operatorname{Re}[q_1 \varphi(z_1) + q_2 \psi(z_2)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

in which

$$p_K = a_{11} \mu_K^2 + a_{12} - a_{16} \mu_K, \quad q_K = \frac{a_{12} \mu_K^2 + a_{22} - a_{26} \mu_K}{\mu_K} \quad (3)$$

$$z_K = x + \mu_K y = r_K \{\cos \theta_K + i \sin \theta_K\} \quad (K = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

with μ_K being the complex roots of the following algebraic equation

$$a_{11} \mu^4 - 2a_{16} \mu^3 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) \mu^2 - 2a_{26} \mu + a_{22} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Now we investigate the plate with edge crack(Fig.1). The stress free boundary conditions on the crack surfaces are

$$\theta = \pm \pi, \quad \sigma_{xy} = 0, \quad \sigma_{yy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

For simplicity, the complex functions $\varphi(z_1)$ and $\psi(z_2)$ are decomposed into two parts[3]

$$\varphi(z_1) = \varphi_1(z_1) + \varphi_2(z_1); \quad \psi(z_2) = \psi_1(z_2) + \psi_2(z_2) \quad (7)$$

which satisfy the conditions $\sigma_{xy} = 0$ and $\sigma_{yy} = 0$ on the uncut portion of the cracked cross section along x-axis, respectively. Considering eq.(1), it can be found that

$$\mu_1 \varphi'_1(\tau) + \mu_2 \psi'_1(\tau) = 0, \quad \varphi'_2(\tau) + \psi'_2(\tau) = 0 \quad (8)$$

where τ represents the value of z_1 and z_2 on x-axis. By means of equations (1), (6) and (8), we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi'_1(z_1) &= \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_1(z_1) + g_1(z_1) \right\}, & \varphi'_2(z_1) &= \frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_2(z_1) + g_2(z_1) \right\} \\ \psi'_1(z_2) &= \frac{-\mu_1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_1(z_2) + g_1(z_2) \right\}, & \psi'_2(z_2) &= \frac{-1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_2(z_2) + g_2(z_2) \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where

$$f_n(z_K) = \sum_{m=0}^M F_{nm} z_K^m, \quad g_n(z_K) = \sum_{m=0}^M G_{nm} z_K^m \quad (10)$$

It is evident that

$$F_{nm} = \bar{F}_{nm}, \quad G_{nm} = -\bar{G}_{nm} \quad (11)$$

i.e. the coefficients F_{nm} are real while G_{nm} are imaginary. For the cracked plate subjected to pin loads, the additional terms are introduced into the complex functions to consider the condition of given resultant forces and single valued condition of displacements surrounding the pin holes, that is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi(z_1) &= \sum_{n=1}^N E_{1n} \ln(z_1 - z_1^{(n)}) + \varphi_1(z_1) + \varphi_2(z_1) \\ \psi(z_2) &= \sum_{n=1}^N E_{2n} \ln(z_2 - z_2^{(n)}) + \psi_1(z_2) + \psi_2(z_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

where N is the number of pin holes and

$$z_K^{(n)} = x^{(n)} + \mu_K y^{(n)} = r_K^{(n)} (\cos \theta_K^{(n)} + i \sin \theta_K^{(n)}) \quad (13)$$

with $x^{(n)}$ and $y^{(n)}$ representing the coordinates for a point in pin hole n .

At first, the condition of given resultant forces at pin holes is taken to be considered. Taking free body from the plate by a cylindrical surface around the hole n (Fig.1) and projecting the forces acting on the cylindrical boundary (C_n) of the element to x - and y -axes, we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_{xn} &= \oint_{C_n} T_x ds = \oint_{C_n} \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} ds \\ &= [\mu_1 \varphi(z_1) + \bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\varphi}(\bar{z}_1) + \mu_2 \psi(z_2) + \bar{\mu}_2 \bar{\psi}(\bar{z}_2)]_{C_n} \\ &= 2\pi i (E_{1n} \mu_1 - \bar{E}_{1n} \bar{\mu}_1 + E_{2n} \mu_2 - \bar{E}_{2n} \bar{\mu}_2) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{yn} &= \oint_{C_n} T_y ds = - \oint_{C_n} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} ds = - [\varphi(z_1) + \bar{\varphi}(\bar{z}_1) + \psi(z_2) + \bar{\psi}(\bar{z}_2)]_{C_n} \\ &= - 2\pi i (E_{1n} - \bar{E}_{1n} + E_{2n} - \bar{E}_{2n}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where U is the stress function.

From above two equations, it can be found that

$$- \frac{R_{1n} + iR_{2n}}{2\pi} = (1 + i\mu_1)E_{1n} - (1 + i\bar{\mu}_1)\bar{E}_{1n} + (1 + i\mu_2)E_{2n} - (1 + i\bar{\mu}_2)\bar{E}_{2n} \quad (16)$$

in which R_{1n} and R_{2n} are used to represent the components of pin load.

Applying eg.(2) and eg.(12), the single valued condition of displacements becomes

$$(u_x + iu_y)|_{C_n} = (p_1 + iq_1)E_{1n} - (\bar{p}_1 + i\bar{q}_1)\bar{E}_{1n} + (p_2 + iq_2)E_{2n} - (\bar{p}_2 + i\bar{q}_2)\bar{E}_{2n} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Considering equations (16) and (17), it can be shown that for orthotropic plate

$$\mu_K = i\beta_K, \quad p_K^I = q_K^R = 0 \quad (K = 1, 2) \quad (18)$$

$$E_{1n}^R = q_2^I R_{1n} / c_1, E_{1n}^I = p_2^R R_{2n} / c_2, E_{2n}^R = -q_1^I R_{1n} / c_1, E_{2n}^I = -p_1^R R_{2n} / c_2 \quad (19)$$

where

$$c_1 = 4\pi(\beta_1 q_2^I - \beta_2 q_1^I), \quad c_2 = 4\pi(p_1^R - p_2^R) \quad (20)$$

with the superscripts R and I denoting the real and imaginary parts of complex coefficients.

$$\text{Assuming } H_m^{(1)} = F_{1m}, \quad H_m^{(2)} = -iG_{1m}, \quad H_m^{(3)} = F_{2m}, \quad H_m^{(4)} = -iG_{2m}$$

and considering equations (1),(2) and (12), the stress and displacement components can be taken in the form

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^* + \sigma_{ij}^{**}, \quad u_i = u_i^* + u_i^{**} \quad (21)$$

with

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^* &= \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{l=1}^4 H_m^{(l)} R_{ijm}^{(l)}, \quad u_i^* = \sum_{m=0}^M \sum_{l=1}^4 H_m^{(l)} S_{im}^{(l)} \\ \sigma_{ij}^{**} &= \sum_{K=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N e_{ijkn} R_{Kn}, \quad u_i^{**} = \sum_{K=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N f_{iKn} R_{Kn} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

where $R_{ijm}^{(l)}, S_{im}^{(l)}, e_{ijkn}$ and f_{iKn} are known functions of r_k and θ_K ($K = 1, 2$) with the material constants as parameters.

3. VARIATIONAL METHOD FOR INVESTIGATION OF S.I.F.

A variational equation obtained from the principle of minimum potential energy assume the form[4]

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi &= - \int_V (\sigma_{ij,j} + F_i) \delta u_i^* dv + \int_{S_T} (\sigma_{ij} n_j - T_i) \delta u_i^* ds + \int_{S_c} (\sigma_{ij} n_j) \delta u_i^* ds \\ &+ \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \int_{S_n} (\sigma_{ij} n_j - T_i) \delta u_i^* ds \right\} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

in which F_i is body force components, S_T the boundary where surface tractions (T_i) are prescribed, S_n ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$) the surfaces of pin holes and n_j the direction cosines. For the cracked plate subjected to pin load, because of the existence of additional terms with respect to pin loads in eq.(21), the integration along the surfaces of crack (S_c) is included. Since the stress and displacement series derived above satisfy all basic equations, we have

$$\int_V (\sigma_{ij,j} + F_i) \delta u_i^* dv = 0 \quad (24)$$

And for the cases of small pin diameters the variation δu_i^* can be considered as unchanged along the hole surfaces. Then, due to the availability of eq.(16), each term

of the summation in eq.(23) can be reduced to

$$\int_{S_n} (\sigma_{ij} n_j - T_i) \delta u_i^* ds = \left\{ \int_{S_n} (\sigma_{ij} n_j - T_i) ds \right\} \delta u_i^* = 0 \quad (25)$$

Finally, considering that the basic terms in the series of stress(σ_{ij}^*) have satisfied the stress-free boundary conditions on the crack surfaces, the variational equation (23) is simplified to

$$\int_{S_T} \sigma_{ij}^* n_j \delta u_i^* ds = - \int_{S_T} (\sigma_{ij}^{**} n_j - T_i) \delta u_i^* ds - \int_{S_C} \sigma_{ij}^{**} n_j \delta u_i^* ds \quad (26)$$

Substituting eq.(22) into above equation, we arrive at the system of algebraic equations for determining the coefficients $H_m^{(l)}$ ($l=1,2,3,4$, $m=0,1,2,\dots,M$). The stress intensity factors, therefore, are given by

$$K_I = \lim_{\substack{\theta \rightarrow 0 \\ r \rightarrow 0}} \sqrt{2\pi r} \sigma_{yy} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} H_0^{(1)}, \quad K_{II} = \lim_{\substack{\theta \rightarrow 0 \\ r \rightarrow 0}} \sqrt{2\pi r} \sigma_{xy} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} H_0^{(3)} \quad (27)$$

Here, r and θ are the polar coordinates with origin at the crack tip.

It can be proved that for Mode I cracking, the undetermined coefficients $H_m^{(2)}$ and $H_m^{(3)}$ ($m=0,1,2,\dots,M$) should be equal to zero. Thus, the algebraic equations to be solved have the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} K^{(11)} & K^{(14)} \\ K^{(41)} & K^{(44)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{H^{(1)}\} \\ \{H^{(4)}\} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \{Q^{(1)}\} \\ \{Q^{(4)}\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

where

$$K_{im}^{(lk)} = \int_{S_T} \left\{ (R_{xxm}^{(k)} n_x + R_{xym}^{(k)} n_y) S_{xi}^{(l)} + (R_{xym}^{(k)} n_x + R_{yym}^{(k)} n_y) S_{yi}^{(l)} \right\} ds \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Q_i^{(l)} = & \int_{S_T} (T_x S_{xi}^{(l)} + T_y S_{yi}^{(l)}) ds \\ & + \sum_{n=1}^N \int_{S_T + S_C} \left\{ \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^2 e_{xxjn} R_{jn} \right) n_x + \left(\sum_{j=1}^2 e_{xyjn} R_{jn} \right) n_y \right] S_{xi}^{(l)} \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^2 e_{xyjn} R_{jn} \right) n_x + \left(\sum_{j=1}^2 e_{yyjn} R_{jn} \right) n_y \right] S_{yi}^{(l)} \right\} ds \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

$(l, k = 1, 4, i, m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M)$

For orthotropic materials, the functions of angle distribution in above equations are found to be

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
(R_{xxm}^{(1)}, R_{yym}^{(1)}) &= \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 (C_{x\kappa}^{(1)}, C_{y\kappa}^{(1)}) r_{\kappa}^{m-\frac{1}{2}} \cos(m-\frac{1}{2})\theta_{\kappa} \\
(R_{xxm}^{(4)}, R_{yym}^{(4)}) &= \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 (C_{x\kappa}^{(4)}, C_{y\kappa}^{(4)}) r_{\kappa}^m \cos m\theta_{\kappa} \\
R_{xym}^{(1)} &= \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 C_{xy\kappa}^{(1)} r_{\kappa}^{m-\frac{1}{2}} \sin(m-\frac{1}{2})\theta_{\kappa}, \quad R_{xym}^{(4)} = \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 C_{xy\kappa}^{(4)} r_{\kappa}^m \sin m\theta_{\kappa} \\
S_{xm}^{(1)} &= \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 D_{x\kappa}^{(1)} \frac{r_{\kappa}^{m+\frac{1}{2}}}{m+\frac{1}{2}} \cos(m+\frac{1}{2})\theta_{\kappa}, \quad S_{xm}^{(4)} = \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 D_{x\kappa}^{(4)} \frac{r_{\kappa}^{m+1}}{m+1} \cos(m+1)\theta_{\kappa} \\
S_{ym}^{(1)} &= \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 D_{y\kappa}^{(1)} \frac{r_{\kappa}^{m+\frac{1}{2}}}{m+\frac{1}{2}} \sin(m+\frac{1}{2})\theta_{\kappa}, \quad S_{ym}^{(4)} = \sum_{\kappa=1}^2 D_{y\kappa}^{(4)} \frac{r_{\kappa}^{m+1}}{m+1} \sin(m+1)\theta_{\kappa}
\end{aligned} \right\} \quad (31)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{x1}^{(1)} &= \frac{-2\beta_1^2\beta_2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{y1}^{(1)} = \frac{2\beta_2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{xy1}^{(1)} = \frac{2\beta_1\beta_2}{\beta_2-\beta_1} \\
C_{x2}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\beta_1\beta_2^2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{y2}^{(1)} = \frac{-2\beta_1}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{xy2}^{(1)} = \frac{-2\beta_1\beta_2}{\beta_2-\beta_1} \\
C_{x1}^{(4)} &= \frac{-2\beta_1^2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{y1}^{(4)} = \frac{2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{xy1}^{(4)} = \frac{2\beta_1}{\beta_2-\beta_1} \\
C_{x2}^{(4)} &= \frac{2\beta_2^2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{y2}^{(4)} = \frac{-2}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad C_{xy2}^{(4)} = \frac{-2\beta_2}{\beta_2-\beta_1} \\
D_{x1}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\beta_2(-a_{11}\beta_1^2+a_{12})}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad D_{y1}^{(1)} = \frac{-2\beta_2(a_{12}\beta_1^2-a_{22})}{\beta_1(\beta_2-\beta_1)} \\
D_{x2}^{(1)} &= \frac{-2\beta_1(-a_{11}\beta_2^2+a_{12})}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad D_{y2}^{(1)} = \frac{2\beta_1(a_{12}\beta_2^2-a_{22})}{\beta_2(\beta_2-\beta_1)} \\
D_{x1}^{(4)} &= \frac{2(-a_{11}\beta_1^2+a_{12})}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad D_{y1}^{(4)} = \frac{-2(a_{12}\beta_1^2-a_{22})}{\beta_1(\beta_2-\beta_1)} \\
D_{x2}^{(4)} &= \frac{-2(-a_{11}\beta_2^2+a_{12})}{\beta_2-\beta_1}, \quad D_{y2}^{(4)} = \frac{2(a_{12}\beta_2^2-a_{22})}{\beta_2(\beta_2-\beta_1)}
\end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

and

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
e_{xx1n} &= -\frac{2}{c_1} \left(\frac{\beta_1^2 q_2^1 V_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{\beta_2^2 q_1^1 V_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right), \quad e_{xx2n} = -\frac{2}{c_2} \left(\frac{\beta_1^2 p_2^R W_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{\beta_2^2 p_1^R W_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right) \\
e_{yy1n} &= \frac{2}{c_1} \left(\frac{q_2^1 V_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{q_1^1 V_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right), \quad e_{yy2n} = \frac{2}{c_2} \left(\frac{p_2^R W_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{p_1^R W_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right) \\
e_{xy1n} &= -\frac{2}{c_1} \left(\frac{\beta_1 q_2^1 W_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{\beta_2 q_1^1 W_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right), \quad e_{xy2n} = \frac{2}{c_2} \left(\frac{\beta_1 p_2^R V_{1n}}{V_{1n}^2 + W_{1n}^2} - \frac{\beta_2 p_1^R V_{2n}}{V_{2n}^2 + W_{2n}^2} \right)
\end{aligned} \right\} \quad (33)$$

with

$$V_{Kn} = r_K \cos \theta_K - r_K^{(n)} \cos \theta_K^{(n)}, \quad W_{Kn} = r_K \sin \theta_K - r_K^{(n)} \sin \theta_K^{(n)} \quad (K = 1,2) \quad (34)$$

in which $r_K^{(n)}$ and $\theta_K^{(n)}$ are the polar coordinates for a point in pin hole n .

Solving equation (28), the 2M unknown coefficients can be obtained. The stress intensity factor for Mode I cracking, therefore, is found from eq.(27).

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The forementioned approach can be used to evaluate the stress intensity factors for the orthotropic plates with edge cracks. Fig.2 shows the edge cracked disc subjected to pin load at (r^*, φ^*) . Referring to Fig.2, the parameters considered in the study are for

$$a / R = 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0,$$

$$1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.5, 1.6$$

$$r^* / R = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, \quad \varphi^* = 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$$

For each possible combination of above set of geometric parameters, the dimensionless S.I.F. ($\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{R} / P$) for edge crack is obtained. Fig.3 to Fig. 6 show the S.I.F. results for various geometry where the material properties are taken to be $E_{11} = 144.8$ GPa, $E_{22} = 11.7$ GPa, $G_{12} = 9.7$ GPa and $\nu_{12} = 0.21$. To investigate the effects of material behaviour, Table 1 shows the convergent results obtained for the cracked disc ($a = R, r^* = 0.64R, \varphi^* = 38.6^\circ$) with variety of material properties. The experimental evidence for the isotropic CT specimen with the same geometry as that in Table 1 presented by Feddern is 6.24 [5]. Good agreement is obtained from numerical and experimental results.

Table 1 The Effects of Material Properties to $\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{W} / P$
 $(W = 1.5R, a = R, r^* = 0.64R, \varphi^* = 38.6^\circ)$

M	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
2	2.807	2.369	2.142	2.155	2.377	2.664	1.618	6.207
3	5.220	4.164	4.138	4.121	3.800	5.048	3.110	8.405
4	6.120	5.217	5.174	5.167	4.873	5.927	4.294	8.696
5	6.122	5.295	5.268	5.262	5.080	5.934	4.456	9.052
6	6.127	5.343	5.359	5.227	5.131	5.935	4.955	9.689
7	6.124	5.378	5.396	5.243	5.125	5.938	5.083	9.766
8	6.126	5.369	5.402	5.241	5.171	5.937	5.082	9.763
E_{11}	200.1	151.6	144.8	144.8	275.8	234.4	122.5	11.7(GPa)
E_{12}	199.9	10.6	11.7	11.7	6.9	144.8	1.0	144.8(GPa)
G_{12}	76.9	5.6	9.7	9.7	3.5	5.2	4.5	9.7(GPa)
ν_2	0.30	0.28	0.21	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.29	0.21

5. CONCLUSION

According to the analysis of theory and the results of computation, it can be seen that the complex variable variational method presents a semi-analytical and semi-numerical approach to evaluate the stress intensity factors for orthotropic plates with edge cracks subjected to pin loads. The key advantage of the method is that the series of stresses and displacements satisfy all of the basic equations exactly. Numerical studies reveal that the convergent and accurate results are given by a quite simple program which reduces data manipulation. And the CPU time for drawing a curve of $\bar{K}_I \approx a/R$ with 17 numerical data only costs 90 seconds.

6. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Orthotropic plate containing an edge crack and subjected to pin loads

FIGURE 2. An edge cracked disc subjected to pin load

FIGURE 3. Relations between normalized S.I.F ($\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{R} / P$) and nondimensional crack length (a/R) for $\varphi^* = 30^\circ$ and different r^*/R ratio ($r^*/R=0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$)

FIGURE 4. Relations between normalized S.I.F ($\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{R} / P$) and nondimensional crack length (a/R) for $\varphi^* = 45^\circ$ and different r^*/R ratio ($r^*/R=0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$)

FIGURE 5. Relations between normalized S.I.F ($\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{R} / P$) and nondimensional crack length (a/R) for $\varphi^* = 60^\circ$ and different r^*/R ratio ($r^*/R = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$)

FIGURE 6. Relations between normalized S.I.F ($\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{R} / P$) and nondimensional crack length (a/R) for $\varphi^* = 75^\circ$ and different r^*/R ratio ($r^*/R = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$)